

Universal single-atom-enhanced catalyst for photocatalytic hydrogen production from water and ammonia

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ABSTRACT

Photocatalytic water splitting and ammonia decomposition are promising industrial approaches for sustainable dihydrogen production. However, the development of a universal photocatalyst capable of efficiently generating dihydrogen from both water and ammonia has remained an unmet challenge. Here, we report a universal Pt single-atom TiO₂/ZnIn₂S₄ heterostructure that integrates 2D chemistry with atomic-level design to enable bifunctional photocatalytic dihydrogen production. This catalyst delivers dihydrogen evolution rates of 108.76 mmol g⁻¹ from water splitting and 12.44 mmol g⁻¹ from aqueous ammonia decomposition after 24 h of continuous irradiation, competitive with state-of-the-art photocatalysts. The bifunctional performance of the catalyst originates from the synergistic interaction among its three components. Atomically dispersed Pt sites, anchored via Pt–S and Pt–O bonds on coordinatively unsaturated sulfur and oxygen sites of ZnIn₂S₄ and TiO₂, respectively, accelerate interfacial reaction kinetics. ZnIn₂S₄ contributes by extending visible-light absorption and optimizing the binding of hydrogen intermediates, while the TiO₂/ZnIn₂S₄ heterojunction ensures efficient separation and migration of photogenerated charge carriers. This study provides a rational design strategy for single-atom-engineered heterostructures toward universal and efficient solar-driven dihydrogen production.

1. Introduction

Photocatalysis offers a promising approach to utilizing solar energy for catalytic reactions, enabling its transformation into high-density chemical fuels [1]. It is an integral part of building a clean and sustainable energy infrastructure, playing a crucial role in achieving carbon neutrality and driving the global energy transition [2]. As a highly efficient energy carrier with a high gravimetric energy density (140 MJ kg⁻¹), dihydrogen (H₂) offers significant environmental advantages, as its combustion emits no greenhouse gases, making it a viable alternative to fossil fuels [3–5].

Among the various approaches, photocatalytic water splitting remains the most widely studied and advanced method for H₂ production using renewable energy sources such as sunlight and water. The core reaction involves the decomposition of water into H₂ and oxygen (O₂):

This process is “thermodynamically non-spontaneous” under standard conditions, requiring an external energy input. The standard Gibbs free energy change (ΔG°) for water splitting is approximately +237.2 kJ/mol, corresponding to a minimum of 1.23 V required per electron

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transferred.

In addition to water, NH₃ has emerged as a highly promising hydrogen carrier. NH₃ offers several advantages: it is easier to store and transport than H₂, particularly at ambient temperatures and pressures. It also possesses a higher volumetric energy density and can leverage existing global infrastructure. These benefits are even more pronounced when waste NH₃, a common pollutant, is utilized as the hydrogen source. NH₃ is a prevalent nitrogen-containing contaminant in wastewater, contributing significantly to eutrophication and O₂ depletion in aquatic systems [6]. While extensively used in industry, its volatility, strong odor, and toxicity pose serious environmental and public health concerns [7]. Regulatory bodies such as the British Health and Safety Executive and the U.S. Occupational Safety and Health Administration have accordingly imposed strict exposure limits—25 ppm (8-h average) and 35 ppm (15-min short-term exposure), respectively [8]. Conventional methods for NH₃ removal, such as breakpoint chlorination or biological nitrification, often generate undesirable by-products like chloramines and nitrates (NO₃⁻). This underscores the pressing need for cleaner and more efficient treatment technologies. From a H₂ production perspective, NH₃ is also attractive because of its high hydrogen content (17.6 wt %), which surpasses common hydrogen carriers such as ethanol, cyclohexane, and liquefied petroleum gas [9]. Its catalytic decomposition offers a carbon-free, sustainable route for H₂ generation. Although this process is thermodynamically uphill, it requires significantly less energy than water splitting, making it suitable for solar-assisted catalysis. The thermodynamic profiles of relevant reactions are as follows: [10].

The fundamental requirements for both photocatalytic processes are quite similar including efficient light absorption, rapid charge separation and transfer of photoinduced carriers to active sites, where the redox reaction occurs [11,12]. Achieving all these parameters simultaneously remains a major challenge in effectively enhancing photocatalytic activity. As a result, the development of highly efficient and durable photocatalysts has been a primary focus for researchers aiming to scale up H₂ production.

Surprisingly, no universal photocatalyst has been reported for the dual decomposition of both NH₃ and water until now. To address this challenge, we combined single-atom engineering with 2D chemistry to create a Pt-single atom enhanced TiO₂/ZnIn₂S₄ heterostructure, which exhibits exceptional dihydrogen production rates in both processes.

In this context, we define a “universal” photocatalyst as a single material platform capable of efficiently and robustly performing bifunctional H₂ generation across chemically distinct feedstocks specifically, water and aqueous ammonia. This is achieved through the utilization of the same photogenerated charge carriers and shared Pt single-atom (Pt-SA) active sites to drive distinct reduction and oxidation cycles. Such dual functionality is both rare and strategically significant, as it bridges the gap between primary green dihydrogen production *via* water splitting and hydrogen release from chemical energy carriers through ammonia photo reforming. Whereas most catalysts are tailored for a single reaction environment, achieving high efficiency in both demonstrates a resilient electronic structure adept at accommodating varying adsorption energies and reaction kinetics.

Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) remains a benchmark photocatalyst due to its non-toxicity, low cost, and excellent stability, but its practical performance is limited by a wide band gap, fast charge recombination, and sluggish proton reduction kinetics [13–18]. Common strategies to address these issues include doping and coupling TiO₂ with narrow-bandgap semiconductors to form heterojunctions that promote directional carrier separation and extend the spectral response [13,17,

19–29]. Representative TiO₂-based heterojunctions have been reported with various visible-light absorbers, including g-C₃N₄, BiOBr, ZnIn₂S₄, -containing composites, WO₃, and BiVO₄ [30–35].

In addition to composition, photocatalyst morphology (size, geometry, and exposed facets) can strongly influence activity [17,24–26, 36–40]. In particular, 2D single-crystalline anatase TiO₂ nanosheets (TNS) with exposed (001) facets provide high surface area and can support facet-dependent charge separation, with electrons and holes preferentially localized on different planes under illumination [17,36, 40–43].

ZnIn₂S₄ (ZIS) is a narrow-bandgap semiconductor with a suitably negative conduction-band potential for proton reduction, favorable H* adsorption, and good stability [43–45]. Its high surface area and strong visible-light absorption make it attractive for photocatalytic applications, and the band alignment between ZIS (E_g = 2.1–2.9 eV) and TNS (E_g = 3.2 eV) is well suited for constructing heterojunctions with enhanced HER activity [18,46–52].

Noble-metal co-catalysts (e.g., Pt, Pd) further boost activity by promoting charge separation and lowering kinetic barriers for H₂ evolution [49,53,54]. Pt is particularly effective, but its scarcity motivates atom-economical designs [22,27,55]. However, its scarcity and cost hinder large-scale use [56].

Single-atom catalysts (SACs) maximize utilization and create isolated active sites that optimize charge distribution and adsorption, and Pt single atoms on semiconductor supports (including TiO₂ and ZIS) have shown pronounced improvements in photocatalytic H₂ generation [22,50,51,53,57–59].

In this work, a reactive dark deposition method was used to anchor Pt single atoms (Pt-SAs) onto a TNS/ZIS heterojunction for H₂ production *via* water splitting and NH₃ decomposition under simulated solar light. A unique heterostructure with an Ohmic-like junction was fabricated using a facile ethylene glycol-assisted solvothermal approach, integrating TNS nanosheets and ZIS nanocubes. The superior photocatalytic performance of the Pt-SAs-TNS/ZIS heterostructure originates from the cooperative roles of its components. ZIS acts as the primary visible-light absorber. The intimate TNS/ZIS interface promotes spatial charge separation and suppresses electron-hole recombination, while atomically dispersed Pt sites anchored through Pt-S and Pt-O bonds on ZIS and TNS serve as electron sinks that facilitate charge extraction and lower the activation barrier for H₂ evolution. As a result, the catalyst exhibits bifunctional activity, achieving H₂ evolution rates of 108.76 mmol g⁻¹ from water splitting and 12.44 mmol g⁻¹ from NH₃ decomposition after 24 of continuous irradiation, underscoring a synergistic architecture for efficient solar-driven H₂ generation.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Reagents and chemicals

Titanium butoxide (TiOBu)₄, ethylene glycol, sodium sulfite (Na₂SO₃), aqueous NH₃, sodium sulfide nonahydrate (Na₂S•9H₂O), Zinc nitrate hexahydrate {Zn(NO₃)₂•6H₂O}, thiourea and Indium (III) nitrate hydrate {In(NO₃)₃•xH₂O} were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Hydrogen fluoride (HF) was obtained from Carl Roth. Platinum precursor (H₂PtCl₆•6H₂O) was supplied by Metakem. Methanol (CH₃OH), from Merck. Deionized (DI) water was used in all the experiments. All chemicals were utilized as received with further purification.

2.2. Synthesis of TNS with reactive (001) facets

In a standard synthesis approach, 10 ml of titanium butoxide was dropped into Teflon liner (250 ml), followed by adding of 1.2 ml of HF with continuous stirring for 40 min. Finally, the hydrothermal autoclave was placed in electric oven at 200 °C for 24 h [40]. The obtained powder was then washed 3 times with ethanol, and DI water after naturally cool down the autoclave and subsequently dried in an oven overnight at

80 °C. The as-synthesized TiO₂ nanosheets are denoted as TNS.

2.3. Synthesis of TNS/ZIS heterojunction

In a typical procedure, a stoichiometric amount of Zinc nitrate hexahydrate, {Zn(NO₃)₂•6H₂O}, thiourea and Indium nitrate hydrate {In(NO₃)₃•xH₂O} were added into Teflon-liner (250 mL) containing ethylene glycol and dispersed amount of TNS and stirred for 2 h at room temperature to make a homogenous mixture. The obtained suspension was then placed in autoclave and heated at 160 °C for 18 h. The powder was washed with DI water and ethanol and dried overnight at 80 °C in oven. The as-prepared heterojunction was named as TNS/ZIS. The pristine ZIS was also synthesized using the same solvothermal approach without adding TNS nanosheets. The product is denoted as ZIS.

2.4. Decoration of Pt single atoms on TNS/ZIS heterostructure

Pt-SAs were decorated onto the TNS/ZIS heterostructure using a facile reactive dark deposition approach [41]. Typically 50 mg of TNS/ZIS heterostructure powder was dispersed in 100 ml aqueous methanol solution (50:50 v/v) containing 0.01 mM H₂PtCl₆•6H₂O. Then the reactor was purged with Ar for 30 min, then stirred at 500 rpm in the dark at room temperature (25 °C) for 24 h. The Pt-SAs deposited TNS/ZIS photocatalyst was collected by centrifugation, washed three times with ethanol and DI water, and dried in oven at 80 °C for 12 h.

2.5. Diffuse reflectance infrared Fourier transform spectroscopy (DRIFTS)

DRIFTS measurements were conducted using a Bruker Vertex FTIR spectrometer equipped with a Praying Mantis™ Harrick DRIFTS cell. Approximately 10 mg of the sample was placed in the sample holder. Prior to measurement, the chamber was evacuated for 30 min to remove physisorbed species. Argon gas was then introduced to establish a clean background, and the baseline spectrum was recorded at resolution of 6 cm⁻¹ using 100 scans. Subsequently, a gas mixture of Ar and CO (10:1 vol ratio) was flowed through the chamber, and infrared spectra were collected during the CO adsorption process. After saturation, CO flow was stopped, and the chamber was purged with pure argon. DRIFT spectra were then recorded during the CO desorption phase. The linear CO stretching band corresponding to CO adsorption on Pt species was monitored to confirm the presence of isolated Pt atoms. All DRIFTS measurements were performed at room temperature.

2.6. Photocatalytic H₂ production via NH₃ decomposing and water splitting

Photocatalytic H₂ production through NH₃ decomposition and water splitting was carried out via an environmentally friendly photocatalytic process within a quartz reactor, using a simulated solar light. In a typical procedure, the as prepared photocatalysts (2 mg) were mixed to aqueous NH₃ solution or distilled water (10 ml) and then the suspension was purged with argon (Ar) for 20 min to remove the unwanted gases and dissolve O₂ in quartz reactor. Finally, quartz reactor was exposed to AM 1.5G solar simulated light (100 mW cm⁻²) with continuous stirring. A 150 W xenon lamp was used as the light source. However, in case of water splitting an aqueous solution of 0.25 M Na₂S + 0.35 M Na₂SO₃ (hole scavenger) was used as a source for the HER, while in aqueous NH₃ solution, no hole scavenger was used. Produced H₂ was measured by gas chromatography (GC-MS-QP20210 SE, Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan) with a thermal conductivity detector (TCD).

2.7. Photoelectrochemical (PEC) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurement

Photoelectrochemical characterization was conducted using a three-

electrode setup. The electrolyte was prepared by mixing deionized water and methanol in a 1:1 vol ratio, followed by the addition of Na₂SO₄ to achieve a concentration of 0.1 M. The working electrode was the FTO substrate coated with the photocatalyst powder, the counter electrode was a platinum wire, and the reference electrode was Ag/AgCl in saturated KCl. Chronoamperometric measurements were carried out using a Gamry potentiostat at an applied potential of 0.5 V vs. Ag/AgCl under both dark and chopped light conditions. The light source used was a 365 nm LED with an intensity of 5 mW cm⁻². Due to the differences in the light sources used, the photocatalytic and PEC data should be compared only qualitatively. EIS measurements were performed with the same setup in the dark over a frequency range of 100 Hz to 0.1 Hz, with an AC amplitude of 10 mV. The bias potential was set to -0.5 V vs. Ag/AgCl, a value close to the flat band potential of the samples.

2.8. Characterization

The surface analysis of synthesized materials was carried out by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Hitachi S4800). The low-resolution imaging morphology of the photocatalysts was analysed using transmission electron microscopy (TEM, JEOL 2010F). High-angle annular dark-field scanning transmission spectroscopy (HAADF-STEM) imaging and EDX (HR-TEM, FEI Titan G2 60-300) elemental mapping was performed at accelerating voltage of 80 kV. The phase purity and crystalline nature of the prepared photocatalysts were performed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) with an X'pert PRO MPD diffraction (Panalytical) with iron-filtered Co K α radiation (40 kV, 30 mA, λ = 0.1789 nm). The ultraviolet-visible diffuse reflectance spectra (UV-DRS) of the prepared photocatalysts were measured by a Specord 250 plus (Analytic Jena, Germany) spectroscopy. The chemical composition and oxidation state of photocatalysts were studied using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS, PHI 5000) Versa probe II XPS system (physical Electronic) with monochromatic Al K α (15 kV, 50 W).

Electrophoretic deposition (EPD) was employed to deposit the photocatalyst powder on fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) glass substrates. Specifically, 2 mg of the powder was ultrasonically dispersed in 50 mL of a solution containing 50 mg of iodine dissolved in acetone. Two FTO substrates, pre-cleaned by sequential sonication in deionized water, ethanol, and acetone (2 min each), were used as the electrodes, with one serving as the cathode and the other as the anode. A constant voltage of 10 V was applied for 10 min to facilitate the deposition. To ensure a uniform and smooth film, the suspension was continuously stirred during the deposition process. After deposition, the samples were rinsed with acetone to remove any residual solution and then dried in air.

3. Results and discussion

The sequential synthesis procedure of the Pt single-atom-decorated TNS/ZIS heterostructure is illustrated in Scheme 1. Initially, anatase TNS with predominantly (001) facets were prepared via the hydrothermal method, as outlined in the experimental section. The addition of HF to the hydrothermal synthesis efficiently stabilized the TNS, resulting formation of a unique (001) crystal plane and generating an F-terminated structure like TiOF₂ (Fig. 1a). These F species play a pivotal role in stabilizing Pt-SAs on the surface of TNS and on the surface of heterostructure (see below).

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was performed to investigate the phase composition and crystallinity of TNS, ZIS, and the TNS/ZIS heterostructure (Fig. 1a). All prepared samples exhibited characteristic diffraction peaks corresponding to anatase TiO₂ (JCPDS #21-1272) [27]. Interestingly, the as-synthesized TNS exhibited an additional peak at $2\theta = 23.61^\circ$ (denoted by *), indicating the presence of the TiOF₂ phase (JCPDS #08-0060) [41]. After ZIS deposition, the anatase phase remained intact; however, new peaks (marked with ■) emerged, confirming the presence of ZIS (ICSD 16200) [60]. Overall, the XRD results confirm the crystalline nature of the synthesized materials and the

Scheme 1. Schematic illustration for the designing of TNS/ZIS heterostructure and decoration of Pt-SAs on it.

Fig. 1. (a) XRD patterns of TNS, ZIS and TNS/ZIS heterostructure, (b–d) HR-SEM images of (b) TNS, (c) ZIS, and (d) TNS/ZIS heterostructure.

successful formation of the heterostructure.

High-resolution Scanning Electron Microscopy (HR-SEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images of TNS, and ZIS cubes are shown in Figs. 1b, c and S1a, b, respectively. These images revealed well-defined morphologies, with TNS displaying predominant (001)

facets of nanosheets and ZIS exhibiting cube-like structures. Figs. 1d and S1c present HR-SEM and TEM images of the TNS/ZIS heterostructure, confirming the successful formation of the interface between TNS and ZIS as also supported by XRD analysis (Fig. 1a). Energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectra of TNS, ZIS, and the TNS/ZIS heterostructure are

presented in Fig. S2a–c, confirming the successful formation of the heterostructure.

To introduce Pt single atoms (Pt–SAs), the TNS/ZIS composite was treated with a 0.01 mM Pt precursor solution in the dark for 24 h using a reactive dark deposition method. The resulting Pt–SAs-decorated TNS/ZIS photocatalyst was characterized by XRD, HR-SEM, and TEM. As anticipated, no distinct Pt-related features were detected in the XRD patterns or in the HR-SEM and TEM images, due to the ultra-small amount of atomic dispersion of Pt (Figs. S3–S5).

To verify Pt–SAs decoration, high-angle annular dark field scanning transmission electron microscopy (HAADF-STEM) imaging and elemental mapping were employed. As shown in Fig. 2a, Pt atoms are predominantly distributed on the surface of the TNS/ZIS heterostructure. These findings, supported by the STEM-EDX elemental mapping, confirm the presence of Pt–SAs homogeneously distributed over the samples (Fig. 2b–h).

Furthermore, Diffuse Reflectance Infrared Fourier Transform Spectroscopy (DRIFTS) using CO as a probe molecule was employed to verify the presence of Pt in SA form (Fig. 2i–k). CO is commonly used to distinguish between different Pt species—such as SAs, clusters, and nanoparticles—based on the characteristic vibrational frequencies of adsorbed CO. A band above 2150 cm^{-1} corresponds to gas-phase CO [55]. The band at approximately 2116 cm^{-1} is typically assigned to linearly adsorbed CO on the support or weakly interacting sites, as it appears consistently in both TNS and ZIS samples. Notably, a peak around 2107 cm^{-1} is attributed to linearly adsorbed CO on positively charged Pt single atoms ($\text{Pt}^{\delta+}$) [61]. The absence of additional peaks associated with bridged or multi-bonded CO species, typically observed at lower wavenumbers, suggests the absence of Pt clusters or nanoparticles. Thus, the data confirm the exclusive presence of atomically

dispersed Pt.

To strengthen our findings and obtain a more detailed quantitative understanding, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was employed to investigate the local structure and coordination environment of Pt single atoms (Pt–SAs). The high-resolution XPS (HR-XPS) spectrum of Zn 2p (Fig. 3a) displays two distinct peaks at 1021.5 and 1044.5 eV, corresponding to Zn $2p_{3/2}$ and $2p_{1/2}$, respectively, confirming the +2 oxidation state of Zn in ZnIn_2S_4 [62,63].

The HR-XPS spectrum of In 3d (Fig. 3b) reveals two peaks at 444.9 and 452.5 eV, attributed to In $3d_{5/2}$ and $3d_{3/2}$, respectively, which indicate the +3 oxidation state for In [43]. Similarly, the S 2p spectrum (Fig. 3c) exhibits peaks at 161.7 and 162.9 eV, assigned to S $2p_{3/2}$ and $2p_{1/2}$, respectively, confirming the presence of S^{2-} species [22,27]. An additional peak at 164.0 eV is attributed to Pt–S bonding, consistent with previous reports [22,27].

The Ti 2p spectrum (Fig. 3d) shows peaks at 458.9 and 464.5 eV, corresponding to Ti $2p_{3/2}$ and $2p_{1/2}$, respectively, confirming the +4 oxidation state of Ti in TiO_2 [25,62]. The O 1s spectrum (Fig. 3e) reveals four components: a main peak at 530.3 eV (lattice O in TiO_2) [64], a peak at 531.9 eV (surface hydroxyl groups), a peak at 532.6 eV (physorbed water or carbonates) [64], and a shoulder at 531.1 eV attributed to surface-coordinated Pt [22,26,27].

The HR-XPS spectrum of Pt 4f (Fig. 3f) shows two primary peaks at 72.54 eV (Pt $4f_{7/2}$) and 75.83 eV (Pt $4f_{5/2}$). These values fall between typical binding energies of Pt^0 (71.3 and 74.6 eV) and Pt^{4+} (72.7 and 76.2 eV), indicating that Pt exists in a partially oxidized state, close to $\text{Pt}^{2+}/\text{Pt}^{4+}$ [27]. Peak deconvolution (using Shirley background, Voigt functions, and 3.29 eV spin-orbit splitting) reveals three distinct chemical states: (i) Pt–S ($4f_{7/2}$ at 72.38 eV), indicating coordination with sulfur atoms in ZIS; (ii) Pt–O ($4f_{7/2}$ at 73.18 eV), suggesting interaction

Fig. 2. (a) HAADF-STEM and HAADF imaging of Pt–SAs decorated TNS/ZIS heterostructure, (b–h) STEM-EDS mappings of Pt–SAs decorated TNS/ZIS heterostructure. (i–k) DRIFTS conducted on TNS, ZIS, and TNS/ZIS/Pt-SA samples.

Fig. 3. HR-XPS and deconvoluted spectra of (a) Zn 2p, (b) In 3d, (c) S 2p, (d) Ti 2p, (e) O 1s, and (f) Pt 4f for Pt-SAs decorated TNS/ZIS heterostructure.

with TiO₂; and (iii) Pt⁴⁺ at 73.96 eV (higher oxidation, supported by Pt@TiO₂ reports of ~74 eV for oxidized Pt beyond Pt²⁺ due to support effects and asymmetry. This progression reflects increasing electron withdrawal from Pt-S to Pt⁴⁺, enhancing catalytic redox activity [22,27,65,66].

These results confirm atomic-scale deposition of Pt onto the TNS/ZIS surface and are consistent with previous studies showing that Pt single atoms preferentially coordinate with sulfur or O atoms—forming Pt-S or Pt-O bonds instead of metallic Pt-Pt clusters [27,67]. This interaction is further supported by the observed Pt-S peak in the S 2p spectrum (Fig. 3c), indicating strong bonding between sulfur species and Pt-SAs.

Altogether, the XPS analysis confirms that both TNS and ZIS serve as anchoring sites for Pt-SAs. These Pt single atoms act as electron trapping centres, promoting vectoral electron transfer from ZIS and TNS to Pt-SAs and thereby suppressing the recombination of photoexcited electron-hole pairs [22,27,68].

Efficient light utilization in semiconductor photocatalysts is essential for enhancing H₂ production. UV-Vis diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (UV-DRS) was employed to investigate the optical properties and estimate the band gaps of the synthesized photocatalysts. As shown in Fig. 4a, pristine TNS exhibit strong UV absorption with an absorption edge around 390 nm. Upon ZIS deposition, a clear red shift in the absorption spectrum was observed, extending the absorption into the visible region. This enhancement is attributed to the photosensitizing effect of ZIS. Moreover, the formation of a heterojunction promotes more efficient sunlight utilization by broadening the absorption range and enhancing the separation of photogenerated charge carriers, which is beneficial for photocatalytic H₂ evolution.

The optical band gaps of pristine TNS, ZIS, TNS/ZIS, and Pt-SAs-decorated TNS/ZIS were estimated using Tauc plots derived from the transformed Kubelka-Munk function as shown in Fig. 4b. The calculated band gap energies were 3.17 eV (TNS), 2.47 eV (ZIS), 2.58 eV (TNS/ZIS), and 2.57 eV (Pt-SAs/TNS/ZIS), respectively.

Further, we evaluated the charge separation capabilities of the as-prepared samples. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was conducted to assess the charge separation efficiency (Fig. 4c). As

summarized in Table S1, the charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) values for TNS, ZIS, and the TNS/ZIS heterojunction were approximately 41.1 kΩ, 14.9 kΩ, and 4.7 kΩ, respectively. The substantial decrease in R_{ct} for the heterojunction indicates enhanced charge transfer efficiency, corroborated by the reduced semi-circular radius observed in the Nyquist plot.

Photocurrent density measurements under chopped illumination further confirm the enhanced performance of the TNS/ZIS heterojunction (Fig. 4d). The heterojunction exhibits a photocurrent density of approximately 178 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$, compared to 136 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ for ZIS and 2.93 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ for TNS. This improvement is attributed to the reduced charge transfer resistance and enhanced charge separation efficiency resulting from heterojunction formation, as evidenced by the EIS measurements (Fig. 4c).

To evaluate the impact of heterojunction formation and Pt single-atom (Pt-SAs) decoration, we conducted photocatalytic H₂ evolution experiments under simulated sunlight for two reactions: water splitting and NH₃ decomposition. For water splitting, Na₂S/Na₂SO₃ were used as sacrificial agents to scavenge photogenerated holes, while NH₃ decomposition was performed without any sacrificial agents to reflect a more practical environmental application.

Fig. 5a summarizes the H₂ production from photocatalytic water splitting using pristine TNS, ZIS, TNS/ZIS heterostructure, and Pt-SAs-decorated TNS/ZIS. The Pt-SAs-decorated sample exhibited the highest H₂ evolution, achieving a cumulative H₂ output of 4886.7 μL representing enhancements of 8.16-, 208.7-, and 646.8-fold compared to TNS/ZIS, ZIS, and TNS, respectively.

To optimize the concentration of Pt single atoms, the photocatalytic H₂ evolution activity was evaluated using different concentrations of Pt precursors (0.001, 0.005, 0.01, and 0.05 mM) under simulated sunlight illumination. As shown in Fig. S6, the sample with 0.01 mM Pt precursor exhibited the highest activity. Fig. S7 presents the photocatalytic H₂ evolution performance of Pt-SAs decorated on TNS and ZIS under the same simulated sunlight conditions. To further assess the role of the heterojunction, Pt-SAs were also deposited on a physical mixture of TNS and ZIS. As evident from Fig. S7, the Pt-SAs deposited on the physically mixed TNS/ZIS heterojunction showed significantly lower activity

Fig. 4. (a) UV-DRS spectra, (b) Tauc plots of pristine, TNS, ZIS, TNS/ZIS, and Pt-SAs decorated TNS/ZIS. (c) EIS measured in the dark at -0.5 V vs. Ag/AgCl. The inset displays the equivalent circuit used for fitting, where RE = reference electrode, R_s = solution resistance, R_{ct} = charge-transfer resistance, CPE = constant-phase element, and WE = working electrode. Experimental data are shown as solid symbols and the impedance fit based on the circuit model is shown as dashed lines. (d) Photocurrent response of TNS, ZIS, and the TNS/ZIS heterojunction under chopped illumination (light on/off cycles).

Fig. 5. (a) Photocatalytic H_2 evolution from water splitting and (b) NH_3 decomposition in the presence of TNS, ZIS, TNS/ZIS, and Pt-SAs decorated TNS/ZIS heterojunction, (c) Reusability and stability of Pt-SAs decorated TNS/ZIS heterostructure.

compared to the integrated heterojunction catalyst, highlighting the importance of the interfacial contact in facilitating charge separation and enhancing photocatalytic activity.

Photocatalytic H_2 experiment was also examined in pure water without sacrificial agents. Fig. S8 exhibits that Pt-SAs decorated TNS/ZIS could still achieve significant H_2 production ($\sim 235.768 \mu\text{L}/24$ h), indicating low but measurable activity that confirms the primary role of the sacrificial agent in enhancing H_2 evolution rates.

Given the promising efficiency of this photocatalyst system in water

splitting, we further assessed its activity for photocatalytic NH_3 decomposition (Fig. 5b). Remarkably, under identical light irradiation conditions and without sacrificial agents, the Pt-SAs-decorated TNS/ZIS photocatalyst again demonstrated the highest performance, reaching a maximum H_2 yield of $559.04 \mu\text{L}$. This corresponds to 2.76-, 10.42-, and 143.39-fold increases relative to TNS/ZIS, ZIS, and TNS, respectively.

The excellent H_2 evolution performance in both systems can be attributed to several synergistic features. First, the TNS/ZIS heterostructure promotes spatial charge separation via interfacial band

alignment, suppressing recombination of photogenerated electron-hole pairs as confirmed by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS, Fig. 4c). Second, the incorporation of Pt single atoms onto the surface forms Schottky junctions that further facilitate charge extraction and lower the activation energy for H₂ evolution. In addition, atomically dispersed Pt sites are known to inhibit H₂/O₂ recombination due to the lack of bi-molecular coordination sites, thus enhancing net H₂ generation. This is supported by previous studies showing that the catalytic performance of Pt species is strongly size-dependent: while nanoparticles are more effective for O₂ dissociation, single atoms are superior in preventing H₂/O₂ recombination, thereby boosting overall photocatalytic efficiency [68–70].

Finally, stability testing over three cycles (Fig. 5c) confirmed the robust performance of the Pt-SAs-decorated TNS/ZIS photocatalyst, which maintaining consistent H₂ evolution over 72 h of continuous operation. Post-stability HAAD-STEM (Fig. S9) and XPS spectra (Fig. S10) analyses indicated no significant structural change. Although Pt leaching was negligible, a slight aggregation of Pt single atoms was observed after photocatalysis.

These results highlight the dual-functional capability of the engineered photocatalyst in efficiently generating H₂ from both water and NH₃, while addressing the additional environmental benefit of NH₃ remediation. The shared enhancement mechanisms underscore the rational design of Pt SA-modified heterostructures for versatile solar-to-fuel conversion applications. Table S2 exhibits the comparative table of our work with previously reported photocatalysts.

Based on experimental analysis and literature reports [25,26], a plausible mechanism for the enhanced photocatalytic H₂ production using the Pt-SAs-decorated TNS/ZIS photocatalyst is proposed and illustrated schematically in Scheme 2.

The band edge positions (E_{CB} and E_{VB}) of TNS, and ZIS were calculated using following Equations (5) and (6) [39,71].

$$E_{CB} = \chi - E^0 - 0.5E_{BG} \quad (5)$$

$$E_{VB} = E_{CB} + E_{BG} \quad (6)$$

where, E_{CB} and E_{VB} represent the conduction and valence edge positions, respectively. χ is the absolute electronegativity of the oxide/sulfide (5.81 eV for TiO₂, [72] and 4.82 eV for ZnInS₄) [73]. E^0 is the free energy of the normal hydrogen electrode (NHE), approximately 4.5 eV. The band gaps of TNS and ZIS, estimated from the Kubelka–Munk plots

(Fig. 4b), were found to be 3.17 eV and 2.47 eV, respectively (see above). The corresponding calculated band edge positions (vs. NHE) are: 0.275, -0.915, 2.895, and 1.55 eV vs. NHE, respectively.

The band alignment and charge transfer processes are illustrated in the energy band diagram in Scheme 2. Upon exposure to simulated sunlight, both TNS and ZIS absorb photons, generating electron-hole pairs. Electrons are excited into the CB of both semiconductors, leaving holes in their VB. Due to internal electric field (IEF), Coulomb interactions, and interfacial band bending, photogenerated electrons transfer from the CB of ZIS to the CB of TNS, while holes migrate from the VB of TNS to the VB of ZIS.

When Pt-SAs are introduced onto the heterostructure, they interact with both semiconductors and serve as electron sinks. These Pt sites accept electrons from the CB of either TNS or ZIS and facilitate the HER. This results in a substantial increase in H₂ production.

In the NH₃ decomposition system (Scheme 2), holes accumulated at either at TNS (VB 2.895 eV) or ZIS (VB 1.55 eV vs. NHE) directly oxidize aqueous NH₃/NH₄OH via dehydrogenation (NH₃/NH₄OH to N₂ + 3H⁺), generating protons that migrate to Pt-SA sites, confirming bifunctional behaviour via shared Pt-SA electron traps but substrate specific oxidation pathways.

Meanwhile, the holes transferred to the VB of ZIS are rapidly consumed by sacrificial agents (e.g., Na₂S/Na₂SO₃) or react with ammonium hydroxide in NH₃-containing systems. This process minimizes electron-hole recombination, prevents photocorrosion, and enhances H₂ evolution. The improved photocatalytic activity thus confirms the effective charge separation and transfer within the Pt-SAs-decorated TNS/ZIS heterostructure, with Pt-SAs acting as key sites for efficient H₂ generation.

4. Conclusion

This study presents a facile strategy to enhance visible-light-driven photocatalysts by engineering a TNS/ZIS heterostructure and decorating it with Pt-SAs. To achieve efficient H₂ production from both water splitting and NH₃ decomposition, Pt-SAs were anchored onto the TNS/ZIS heterostructure using a reactive dark deposition approach. This method stabilizes positively charged Pt-SAs by forming Pt-S and Pt-O bonds on coordinatively unsaturated sulfur and oxygen atoms, significantly improving photocatalytic performance. The optimized Pt-SAs/TNS/ZIS photocatalyst exhibited H₂ evolution rates of 108.76 mmol g⁻¹

Scheme 2. Possible charge separation and transfer mechanism of the photocatalytic H₂ from water and NH₃ decomposition over Pt-SA decorated TNS/ZIS semiconductor photocatalyst under AM 1.5G illumination.

from water splitting and 12.44 mmol g⁻¹ from aqueous NH₃ decomposition after 24 of continuous irradiation under simulated solar light. This enhanced activity is attributed to improved light absorption, efficient charge separation, and carrier transport within the Pt-SA-doped heterojunction-based nanocomposite. Additionally, Pt-SAs accelerate interfacial reaction kinetics, leading to a substantial increase in overall photocatalytic efficiency. The formation of Pt-S/Pt-O bonds in the TNS/ZIS photocatalyst ensures stability for up to 72 h without loss of photocatalytic activity. These findings underscore the crucial role of surface coordinated Pt²⁺ species in achieving high photocatalytic efficiency at minimal Pt loading (0.01 mM). This study introduces a promising strategy for designing single-atom-assisted heterojunction photocatalysts capable of efficient hydrogen production from multiple sources under simulated sunlight.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Waseem Raza: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **S.M. Hossein Hejazi:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Lukáš Zdražil:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Data curation. **Thamra Alshahrani:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Radek Zboril:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Štěpán Kment:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2026.154592>.

Data availability

Upon acceptance of the manuscript the following statement will be included in the article: “The source data supporting the findings of this work are freely available in Zenodo findable under the same title.”

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